

Preliminary Discussion on Dynamic Causal Bayesian Optimisation with Prior Knowledge

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Abstract

We propose $\text{DC}\pi\text{BO}$ — Dynamic Causal Bayesian Optimisation with Prior Knowledge — that enhances the performance of Dynamic Causal Bayesian Optimisation (DCBO), a method used for optimising black-box functions — without relying on convexity or other properties — for which dynamic and causal relationships among the function’s variables are known, such as complex economic models. We show that $\text{DC}\pi\text{BO}$ outperforms existing state-of-the-art methods in the DCBO field by allowing domain experts to incorporate prior knowledge — expressed as a function — into the optimisation process. Such a function indicates where they believe the optimal values are located. Instead of blindly searching for optimal points, $\text{DC}\pi\text{BO}$ evaluates the provided function at different points to inform its search. When domain experts provide accurate prior knowledge, $\text{DC}\pi\text{BO}$ demonstrates better performance compared to other existing approaches. In our experimental analysis, which includes both synthetic and real datasets, we see that even when our expert-provided priors are not perfectly precise, $\text{DC}\pi\text{BO}$ still produces results that are comparable to competing methods.

1. Introduction

This paper proposes $\text{DC}\pi\text{BO}$, a novel algorithm for Dynamic Causal Bayesian Optimisation with Prior Knowledge. It is an optimisation technique designed to deal with black-box functions — without relying on convexity or other properties — for which dynamic and causal relationships among the function’s variables are known.

For instance, consider the problem of minimising the *unemployment rate* (target variable) in a closed economy (Aglietti et al., 2021). Decision makers can decide which variables to manipulate, *e.g.*, the *inflation rate* and the *fiscal policy*. Such two variables — jointly with an exogenous one, *economic growth* — can affect the *unemployment rate*.

In this paper, **we propose $\text{DC}\pi\text{BO}$** (Section 3) that extends an existing recent proposal (Aglietti et al., 2021) for Dynamic Causal Bayesian Optimisation (DCBO) (Section 2). $\text{DC}\pi\text{BO}$ enables domain experts to express a prior as a function that specifies where they believe the location of the optima to be. The prior does not need to be numerically precise but somewhat indicative. $\text{DC}\pi\text{BO}$ then evaluates such a given function in the search for optima.

Our extensive experimental analyses (Sections 4 and 5) — which include both synthetic and real-world datasets — show that when the domain expert provides accurate priors, $\text{DC}\pi\text{BO}$ outperforms competing approaches while producing comparable results when imprecise priors are provided. Also, using an imprecise prior does not cause any drawbacks

compared to DCBO: computation time and resources are very similar, making the difference negligible. We also report on post-hoc analyses (Section 5.3) to illustrate the impact of the algorithm’s hyperparameters on the optimisation results.

Our contributions are the following:

1. We propose DC π BO, a novel algorithm for Dynamic Causal Bayesian Optimisation with Prior Knowledge;
2. We show that DC π BO performs statistically significantly better ($p < 0.01$) than state-of-the-art algorithms when the domain expert provides accurate priors;
3. We show that DC π BO is statistically analogous ($p > 0.01$) to state-of-the-art algorithms when the domain expert provides imprecise priors, far from the real optima.

All datasets we consider in our analysis (Section 4.1) are already publicly available.

2. Background

Bayesian Optimisation (BO) (Frazier, 2018) is an optimisation technique typically used with continuous functions $f(\mathbf{x})$ operating over data points with low dimensionality, *i.e.*, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ with $d \leq 20$. BO is particularly effective when the cost of evaluating such a function is high, typically because there is the need to interact with a *black-box* system or simulator. It is, therefore, necessary to identify a derivative-free optimisation procedure as—*a priori*—it is unknown whether such a function is convex or linear.

BO presents itself as a lively research topic, as testified by the numerous papers discussed in this work, as well as other complimentary works employing some forms of Bayesian optimisation as the main building block of the research, such as investigating the use of BO in environments with high dimensionality (Wang et al., 2016) and for building multi-objective optimisation algorithms (Iqbal et al., 2023).

Causal Inference (CI) (Pearl, 2012) leverages the causal model associated with an equation to exploit observational and interventional distributions. *Observational distributions* are samples of a system evolving under normal conditions, *i.e.*, unaffected by external interventions. The observational conditional $p(Y = y \mid X = x)$ looks at the distribution of Y given the observation that the variable X takes the value x . *Interventional distributions* are samples of a system evolving under the influence of an external agent via the do-calculus (Pearl, 2012). $p(Y = y \mid \text{do}(X = x))$ looks at the distribution of Y given that the variable X is *purposely set* to take value x . This describes the distribution of Y one would observe if they intervened by forcing X to take the value x without affecting the other variables.

Causal Bayesian Optimisation (CBO) (Aglietti et al., 2020) generalises BO— which treats all variables as independent— exploiting their causal relationships and solves the problem of globally optimising a function according to a variable of interest. In dynamic systems, however, deciding how to intervene at every point in time is particularly complex due to the evolving nature of causal effects.

Dynamic Causal Bayesian Optimisation (DCBO) (Aglietti et al., 2021) accounts for both the causal relationships among input variables and the causality between inputs and outputs, which might evolve. DCBO integrates CBO with Dynamic Bayesian

Networks (DBNs) (Koller & Friedman, 2009), which, instead, consider dependencies among variables that are not necessarily causal.

DCBO can find an optimal sequence of interventions accounting for the system’s causal and temporal dynamics. It also considers past optimal interventions, thus identifying the optimal intervention faster and at a lower cost.

DCBO uses a probabilistic causal model consisting of a Structural Causal Model (SCM) with an associated Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) \mathcal{G} that encodes the knowledge of the dynamic and causal relationships among the variables and is assumed to be known. A SCM M is a triple $\langle \mathbf{U}, \mathbf{V}, \mathbf{F} \rangle$, where:

\mathbf{U} is a set of independent exogenous variables determined by factors outside of the model;

\mathbf{V} is a set of endogenous variables, including:

- *Non-manipulative variables* \mathbf{C} , which cannot be modified;
- *Treatment variables* \mathbf{X} that can be set to specific values;
- *Output variables* \mathbf{Y} that represent variables of interest for the agent;

\mathbf{F} is a set of functions $\{f_1, \dots, f_n\}$ such that each $f_i : U_i \cup \text{PA}(V_i) \rightarrow V_i$, where $U_i \subseteq \mathbf{U}$ and $\text{PA}(V_i) \subseteq \mathbf{V} \setminus V_i$ is the set of parents of V_i in \mathcal{G} , and the entire set F forms a mapping from \mathbf{U} to \mathbf{V} . In other words, each $\{f_i \in v_i \leftarrow f_i(\text{PA}(V_i), u_i) \mid i = 1, \dots, n\}$ assigns a value to V_i that depends on the values of the selected set of variables $U_i \cup \text{PA}(V_i)$.

The goal of DCBO is to find a sequence of interventions, optimising a target variable at each time step in a causal dynamic DAG. Given \mathcal{G}_t and M_t at step t , the method optimises Y_t by intervening on a subset of the manipulative variables \mathbf{X}_t . The optimal intervention variables $\mathbf{X}_{s,t}^*$ and intervention levels $\mathbf{x}_{s,t}^*$ are given by:

$$\mathbf{X}_{s,t}^*, \mathbf{x}_{s,t}^* = \underset{\mathbf{X}_{s,t}, \mathbf{x}_s}{\text{argmin}} \mathbb{E}[Y_t \mid do(\mathbf{X}_{s,t} = \mathbf{x}_{s,t}), \mathbb{1}_{t>0} \cdot I_{0:t-1}] \quad (1)$$

where

- $\mathbf{X}_{s,t} \in 2^{\mathbf{X}_t}$, $\mathbf{x}_s \in D(\mathbf{X}_{s,t})$;
- $I_{0:t-1} = \bigcup_{i=0}^{t-1} do(\mathbf{X}_{s,i}^* = \mathbf{x}_{s,i}^*)$ denotes previous interventions;
- $\mathbb{1}_{t>0}$ is the indicator function;
- $D(\mathbf{X}_{s,t})$ represents the domain of possible interventions for $\mathbf{X}_{s,t}$.

Solving (1) requires three assumptions, which may limit the use of DCBO and methods derived from it:

1. Invariance of causal structure: $\mathcal{G}(t) = \mathcal{G}(0) \forall t > 0$;
2. Additivity of $f_{Y_t}(\cdot)$: $Y_t = f_{Y_t}(\text{PA}(Y_t)) + \epsilon$, with $f_{Y_t}(\text{PA}(Y_t)) = f_Y^Y(Y_t^{\text{PT}}) + f_Y^{\text{NY}}(Y_t^{\text{PNT}})$, where f_Y^Y and f_Y^{NY} are two generic unknown functions, and $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$;
3. Absence of unobserved confounders in $\mathcal{G}_{0:T}$;

where $\mathcal{G}(t)$ is the causal graph including variables at time t in $\mathcal{G}_{0:T}$; $Y_t^{\text{PT}} = \text{PA}(Y_t) \cap Y_{0:t-1}$ is the set of variables in $\mathcal{G}_{0:T}$ that are both parents of Y_t and targets at previous time steps; $Y_t^{\text{PNT}} = \text{PA}(Y_t) \setminus Y_t^{\text{PT}}$ is the complement; and $f_{Y_t}(\cdot)$ is the functional mapping for Y_t in M_t .

At each time step t and for each $\mathbf{X}_{s,t} \in \mathbb{M}_t$, where \mathbb{M}_t is the search space at time t , the objective function $f_{s,t}(\mathbf{x})$ is then represented as a Gaussian Process (GP)

$$f_{s,t}(\mathbf{x}) \sim \mathcal{GP}(m_{s,t}(\mathbf{x}), k_{s,t}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')) \quad (2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} m_{s,t}(\mathbf{x}) &= \mathbb{E} \left[f_Y^Y(\mathbf{f}^*) + \hat{\mathbb{E}}[f_Y^{NY}(\mathbf{x}^{\text{PY}}, \mathbf{i}^{\text{PY}}, \mathbf{w})] \right] \\ k_{s,t}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') &= k_{\text{RBF}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') + \sigma_{s,t}(\mathbf{x})\sigma_{s,t}(\mathbf{x}') \\ \sigma_{s,t}(\mathbf{x}) &= \sqrt{\mathbb{V} \left[f_Y^Y(\mathbf{f}^*) + \hat{\mathbb{E}}[f_Y^{NY}(\mathbf{x}^{\text{PY}}, \mathbf{i}^{\text{PY}}, \mathbf{w})] \right]} \end{aligned}$$

and $\hat{\mathbb{E}}[f_Y^{NY}(\mathbf{x}^{\text{PY}}, \mathbf{i}^{\text{PY}}, \mathbf{w})]$ represents the expected value of $p(\mathbf{w} \mid \text{do}(\mathbf{X}_{s,t} = \mathbf{x}), \mathbf{i})$ which is estimated via the do-calculus using observational data. The outer expectation in $m_{s,t}(\mathbf{x})$ and the variance in $\sigma_{s,t}(\mathbf{x})$ are computed with respect to $p(f_Y^Y, f_Y^{NY})$, which is also estimated using observational data. Here f_Y^Y, f_Y^{NY} and all functions in the SCM are modelled by independent GPs.

Given the objective function modelled as a GP at time t , the agent selects the interventions to implement by solving a CBO problem. The agent explores the search space \mathbb{M}_t and decides where to intervene by maximising an **acquisition function**. In this paper, we consider the causal Expected Improvement as acquisition function:

$$\text{EI}_{s,t}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\mathbb{E}_{p(y_{s,t})}[\max(y_{s,t} - y_t^*, 0)]}{\text{cost}(\mathbf{X}_{s,t}, \mathbf{x}_{s,t})} \quad (3)$$

where y_t^* is the optimal observed target value in $\{Y_{s,t}^I\}_{s=1}^{|\mathbb{M}_t|}$, that is the optimal observed target across all intervention sets at time t . The division by the cost $\text{cost}(\mathbf{X}_{s,t}, \mathbf{x}_{s,t})$ is performed to maximise the improvement per cost unit at each iteration.

Given $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{|\mathbb{M}_t|}$, solutions of the optimisation of $\text{EI}_{s,t}(\mathbf{x})$ for each set in \mathbb{M}_t , the value to consider is thus (s^*, α^*) , where

$$s^* = \underset{s \in \{1, \dots, |\mathbb{M}_t|\}}{\text{argmax}} \alpha_s$$

and

$$\alpha^* := \max\{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{|\mathbb{M}_t|}\}.$$

While it is true that this approach shows exploitative behaviour due to myopia (Garnett, 2023), EI Equation (3) is still the most commonly used acquisition function in Bayesian Optimisation (Moćkus, 1975). A full experimental comparison with other approaches, like dynamic programming-based ones, is outside the scope of this paper, as it focuses on the embedding of prior knowledge in the optimisation procedure.

At time t , the agent implements H exploratory interventions in the system, which are selected by maximising the causal Expected Improvement. Once the budget H is exhausted,

the agent implements *the decision intervention* I_t , which is the optimal intervention found at the current time step and moves forward to a new optimisation at $t + 1$ carrying the information in $y_{0:t-1}^*$. The parameter H determines the level of exploration of the system and acts as a budget for the CBO algorithm, and is typically problem-specific.

For any set $\mathbf{X}_{s,t} \in \mathbb{M}_t$, the distribution $p(f_{s,t} \mid \mathcal{D}_{s,t}^I)$ will also be a GP — *cf.*, Equation (2) — with parameters

$$m_{s,t}(\mathbf{x} \mid \mathcal{D}_{s,t}^I) = m_{s,t}(\mathbf{x}) + k_{s,t}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{X}^I)[k_{s,t}(\mathbf{X}^I, \mathbf{X}^I) + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}](\mathbf{Y}_{s,t}^I - m_{s,t}(\mathbf{X}^I))$$

and

$$k_{s,t}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}' \mid \mathcal{D}_{s,t}^I) = k_{s,t}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') - k_{s,t}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{X}^I)[k_{s,t}(\mathbf{X}^I, \mathbf{X}^I) + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}]k_{s,t}(\mathbf{X}^I, \mathbf{x}').$$

3. Our Proposal to Exploit Prior Knowledge in DC π BO

The primary contribution of this paper — DC π BO (Algorithm 1), which extends the existing DCBO proposal (Aglietti et al., 2021) — is to enable domain experts to express and leverage prior knowledge about the optimal solutions. This is inspired by a paper (Hvarfner et al., 2022), where prior knowledge is leveraged when dealing with pure BO.

A prior π is a user-specified prior probability on the location of the optimum:

$$\pi(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbb{P} \left(f(\mathbf{x}) = \min_{\mathbf{x}' \in \mathcal{X}} f(\mathbf{x}') \right) \quad (4)$$

This prior acts as a weighting scheme on the points of the search space and can be combined with an acquisition function α to form a prior-weighted version of the specific chosen function. Hence:

$$\mathbf{x}_n \in \operatorname{argmax}_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}} \alpha(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{D}_n) \cdot \pi(\mathbf{x}). \quad (5)$$

In the presence of imprecise priors, the trust in them should decrease over time through a *Decay Policy* (Hvarfner et al., 2022). The prior has $\gamma_h \in \mathbb{R}^+$ as an exponent, which decays toward zero with growing h — with h being the current iteration of the causal cycle. The resulting prior reflects the loss of confidence towards it as the iterations progress and is:

$$\pi_h(\mathbf{x}) = \pi(\mathbf{x})^{\gamma_h} = \pi(\mathbf{x})^{\frac{\beta}{h}}. \quad (6)$$

In particular, $\beta \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is a hyperparameter set by the user, reflecting the confidence in the prior.

Thus, the acquisition function becomes:

$$\alpha_{\pi,h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{D}_n) \triangleq \alpha(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{D}_n)\pi_h(\mathbf{x}) \triangleq \alpha(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{D}_n)\pi(\mathbf{x})^{\frac{\beta}{h}} \quad (7)$$

The likelihood of prior knowledge being available is linked to each optimisation task and the users' experience with similar endeavours: prior knowledge is very likely when dealing with previously encountered similar problems, whilst less likely for new and unexplored problems. The prior is intended as a guide for the search, not in a predictive way that suggests the actual numerical results to the algorithm. Thus, the prior only needs to be behaviourally accurate in relationship with other parameters, not numerically precise, making it more likely to be available.

Algorithm 1 Dynamic Causal Bayesian Optimisation with Prior Beliefs - **DC π BO**

Require: $\mathcal{D}^O, \{\mathcal{D}_{s,t=0}^I\}_{s \in \{0, \dots, |\mathbb{M}_0|\}}, \mathcal{G}_{0:T}, H$, a function f_{UB} representing the user belief about the location of the optima

- 1: Initialise $\mathbb{M}, \mathcal{D}_0^I$, initial optimal $\mathcal{D}_*^I = \emptyset$
- 2: Compute all the priors π_h from the given behaviour f_{UB}
- 3: **for** $t = 0, \dots, T$ **do**
- 4: Initialise dynamic causal GP models for all $\mathbf{X}_{s,t} \in \mathbb{M}_t$ using $\mathcal{D}_{*,t-1}^I$ if $t > 0$
- 5: Initialise interventional dataset $\{\mathcal{D}_{s,t}^I\}_{s \in \{0, \dots, |\mathbb{M}_t|\}}$
- 6: **for** $h = 1, \dots, H$ **do**
- 7: Compute $\text{EI}_{s,t}(\mathbf{X})$ for each $\mathbf{X}_{s,t} \in \mathbb{M}_t$
- 8: Compute $\text{EI}_{s,t,\pi}(\mathbf{x})$
- 9: Obtain (s^*, α^*)
- 10: Intervene and augment $\mathcal{D}_{s=s^*,t}^I$
- 11: Update posterior for $f_{s=s^*,t}$
- 12: **end for**
- 13: Identify the optimal intervention $(\mathbf{X}_{s,t}^*, \mathbf{x}_{s,t}^*)$
- 14: Append optimal interventional data $\mathcal{D}_{*,t}^I = \mathcal{D}_{*,t-1}^I \cup ((\mathbf{X}_{s,t}^*, \mathbf{x}_{s,t}^*), y_t^*)$
- 15: **end for**

DC π BO, described in Algorithm 1, requires an observational dataset, a SCM for the problem, a budget H , and, prior knowledge to be translated into the actual prior. The first step (line 1) initialises the search space from the given requirements, builds the required interventional datasets, such as the one for the optimal interventions, and takes as input the prior, *i.e.*, a function specified by the user, which defines where they believe the location of the optima to be. Next, having such a prior function, the algorithm automatically derives the actual priors π_h from it, by sampling (line 2). It considers the *Decay Policy* to produce $T \times H$ values for the prior, one for each step of the two following iterations.

After the initialisation stage, Algorithm 1 executes the external cycle looking at the dynamic component of the optimisation problem (lines 3–15). For each time step, Algorithm 1 computes (lines 4–5) the dynamic causal GP models for all intervention variables of the search space using the data from the previous best interventions, if available, and initialises the current intervention dataset.

Then, Algorithm 1 begins an inner cycle for the causal component (lines 6–12), which is executed as many times as the budget H allows. Here Algorithm 1 performs the main prior-related computations: it computes the expected improvement for each variable (line 7), to which apply the prior (line 8), *cf.*, Equation (7). Algorithm 1 chooses the variable whose intervention causes the best improvement (line 9), applies and stores the relative intervention (line 10), and updates the GP model for the objective function (line 11).

Algorithm 1 then identifies the best intervention for each time step (line 13) and produces a sequence of the best interventions chosen to reach the optimisation solution alongside the obtained values of the objective function.

Figure 1: SCMs for the synthetic experiments

4. Experimental Design

We compare Algorithm 1 with DCBO (Aglietti et al., 2021) on a large variety of optimisation problems (Section 4.1). We then discuss the primary metric used for comparing the results (Section 4.2), and the research hypotheses we will test (Section 4.3).

4.1 Benchmarking Optimisation Problems

In line with the literature, we consider four synthetic optimisation problems (Section 4.1.1) and three realistic (Section 4.1.2).

4.1.1 SYNTHETIC EXPERIMENTS

We consider four different variations of a starting synthetic experiment, initially introduced in (Aglietti et al., 2021), whose DAGs associated to their SCMs are depicted in Figure 1:

STAT A base, stationary experiment, with graph structure and the structural causal model independent of time (Figure 1a).

IND A variation of the STAT experiment. Both variables act independently upon the output instead of one acting upon the other. Note the change of arrows' directions in Figures 1a and 1b.

MULTIV This is a modification to the IND experiment. A new variable is introduced, which acts upon one previously existing variable (Figure 1c).

NONSTAT This is a modification to the STAT experiment. Here, both the graph structure and the structural causal model change over time. This is implemented by having at each time step a variable acting upon a different one at the next time step (*e.g.*, $X_0 \rightarrow Z_1 \rightarrow Y_2$, Figure 1d).

4.1.2 REAL-WORLD EXPERIMENTS

Of the following experiments, ODE and ECON are based on real use cases, adapted from a previous work (Aglietti et al., 2021), while PISCHAT was proposed in a paper (Andrew et al., 2022) as an application of DCBO in the context of Active Cyber Defence.

ODE This optimisation problem builds upon a study (Blasius et al., 2020) on biological systems in which two species interact, one as a predator and the other as a prey. In the original work (Blasius et al., 2020), the authors wanted to demonstrate the potential indefinite persistence of a predator-prey system. The experiment uses the structural causal model of the ordinary differential equations (ODE) provided in the same paper (Blasius et al., 2020), describing a predator-prey community in a chemostat, a tool to cultivate microorganisms with pre-defined and constant conditions. As the observational dataset, the experimental data collected *in vitro* are used. The DAG associated with the SCM for the experiment can be observed in Figure 2a. It is used to investigate a requisite intervention policy necessary to reduce the concentration of dead subjects in the chemostat. In particular, one can manipulate $N_{in,t}$, *i.e.*, the concentration of the prey in the external medium, J_t , *i.e.*, the concentration of juvenile predators, and A_t , *i.e.*, the concentration of adult predators. We observe the effects on the output variable D_t , *i.e.*, the concentration of dead subjects. N_t , *i.e.*, the prey concentration, P_t , *i.e.*, the general predator concentration, and E_t , *i.e.*, the predator egg concentration are exogenous.

PISCHAT In the original idea (Andrew et al., 2022), the authors consider the problem of active cyber security building upon a simulator and models for causal decision-making through optimisation. The chosen causal structure (Andrew et al., 2022) is provided in Figure 2b. The simulator is then used to provide observational data.

(a) SCM for the ODE experiment

(b) SCM for the PISCHAT experiment

ECON Let us now continue with the example introduced in Section 1 about minimising the unemployment rate of a closed economy, originally proposed in another work (Aglietti et al., 2021). The observational dataset is obtained by extracting data from the OECD portal¹ looking at:

- **GDP**, *i.e.*, GDP in millions of US dollars;
- **CPI**, *i.e.*, annual growth of inflation measured by consumer price index CPI;
- **TAXREV**, *i.e.*, tax revenues measured as a percentage of GDP;
- **HUR**, *i.e.*, unemployment rate as measured by the number of unemployed people as a percentage of the labour force.

These indicators are then manipulated to get the nodes for the directed acyclic graph:

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_t &= \log(\text{HUR}_t) \\
 T_t &= \frac{\text{TAXREV}_t \cdot \text{GDP}_t - \text{TAXREV}_{t-1} \cdot \text{GDP}_{t-1}}{\text{TAXREV}_{t-1} \cdot \text{GDP}_{t-1}} \\
 G_t &= \frac{\text{GDP}_t - \text{GDP}_{t-1}}{\text{GDP}_{t-1}} \\
 I_t &= \text{CPI}_t
 \end{aligned}$$

where we can manipulate I_t , *i.e.*, the *inflation rate*, and T_t , *i.e.*, the *fiscal policy*, while G_t —the *economic growth*—is exogenous. Figure 3 depicts the DAG associated with the SCM building upon the following variables with additional random noise:

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_t &= f_T(t) + \epsilon_T \\
 I_t &= f_I(t) + \epsilon_I \\
 G_t &= f_G(T_t, I_t) + \epsilon_G \\
 U_t &= f_U(G_t, I_t) + \epsilon_U.
 \end{aligned}$$

4.2 Performance Metric

As proposed in (Aglietti et al., 2021), we run each optimisation problem multiple times, and the results are used to compute the values of a **gap metric** defined as:

$$G_t = \left[\frac{y(\mathbf{x}_{s,t}^*) - y(\mathbf{x}_{\text{init}})}{y^* - y(\mathbf{x}_{\text{init}})} + \frac{H - H(\mathbf{x}_{s,t}^*)}{H} \right] \left[\frac{2H - 1}{H} \right]^{-1} \quad (8)$$

where $y(\cdot)$ represents the evaluation of the objective function, y^* is the global minimum, \mathbf{x}_{init} is the first evaluated point, and $\mathbf{x}_{s,t}^*$ is the best evaluated point. $0 \leq G_t \leq 1$, with higher values denoting better performances.

The term $\frac{H - H(\mathbf{x}_{s,t}^*)}{H}$ —with $H(\mathbf{x}_{s,t}^*)$ denoting the number of exploratory attempts needed to reach $\mathbf{x}_{s,t}^*$ —captures the convergence rate of the optimisation procedure to the optimum. This term is zero when the algorithm does not converge, and $\frac{H-1}{H}$ when the algorithm converges at the first attempt.

¹OECD Data Portal: <http://data.oecd.org>

Figure 3: SCM for the ECON experiment

4.3 Research Hypotheses

We test the following two research hypotheses:

- H1** When initialised with an *accurate prior*, the *gap metric*, Equation (8), when using Algorithm 1 is statistically higher than DCBO;
- H2** When initialised with an *imprecise prior*, the *gap metric*, Equation (8), when using Algorithm 1 does not return statistically different results than DCBO.

With **H1**, we test the performance of Algorithm 1 in the optimal condition of receiving prior knowledge where the domain expert effectively chooses either the right optimum or a close neighbour. In this situation, we expect Algorithm 1 to statistically outperform DCBO.

When, however, the domain expert chooses an imprecise prior, we expect Algorithm 1 to perform analogously to DCBO; hence the difference in performance between the two algorithms should not be statistically different (**H2**).

In the implementation, the prior knowledge is an array of values chosen by the domain expert, specifying the value of the optima at each time step. For the synthetic experiments, except for NONSTAT, the prior knowledge is a mathematical function—specifically a line in the slope-intercept form—on which the values of the optima lie at each time step. For the realistic experiments and for NONSTAT, the array contains the actual values of the optima. A limited Gaussian noise $\epsilon = \mathcal{N}(0, 0.1)$ is then added to all values. The imprecise priors are sampled from a uniform distribution derived by a pseudo-random generation algorithm.

5. Experimental Results

In this section, we present the results of our tests. First, we describe the setup used for the experimentation and then proceed to explain such results. We also offer a discussion regarding the hyperparameters used in the experiments, their significance, and their contributions.

5.1 Experimental Setup

Our experimental analysis is built upon the publicly available code published by the authors of DCBO (Aglietti et al., 2021). Our code is available online on GitHub and is released with the MIT license.^{2,3}

We performed the experiments on a Ubuntu-based system (version 22.04 LTS), running Python 3.10. The machine employed a Ryzen 7 2700X CPU overclocked at 4100MHz, an Nvidia 2080Ti GPU, and 64GB of DDR4 RAM overclocked at 3000Mhz. Further details on all the employed packages are available in GitHub repositories.

In addition to comparing Algorithm 1—marked as DC π BO—against DCBO (Aglietti et al., 2021) (*cf.*, Section 4.3), we also compare against the pure BO algorithm (Frazier, 2018) and the π BO proposal (Hvarfner et al., 2022). While BO and π BO do not provide specific treatment of the dynamic part of some optimisation problems we consider, *cf.*, Section 4.1, they are nevertheless very interesting benchmarking. For a fair comparison, we initialised both π BO and DC π BO with the same prior knowledge for each run.

For each of the domains illustrated in Section 4.1, we ran each of the four algorithms—BO, π BO, DCBO and DC π BO—ten times, and considered their gap metric (*cf.*, Section 4.2). Each algorithm has been re-implemented to avoid running code building on different versions of the same library, thus trying to reduce such biases. Our tests show negligible differences with the code available for the existing approaches. As a minor note, even when using the original code by the authors of DCBO (Aglietti et al., 2021) without any modifications or additions, we have not been able to produce results identical to their reported ones.

All experiments have been performed with the same value for the hyperparameters: $\beta = 1$ (*cf.*, Algorithm 1) and $T = 3$, *i.e.*, the number of timesteps of the optimisation procedure. These are the same hyperparameters also used in the testing of DCBO (Aglietti et al., 2021).

For each experiment, we present the average and standard deviations and the averaged percentage difference when introducing the prior. We test our research hypotheses using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test (Wilcoxon, 1945).

5.2 Hypotheses Testing

For each optimisation problem discussed in Section 4.1, for each of the four algorithms considered—BO, π BO, DCBO and DC π BO—Table 1 displays the averaged gap metric and the standard deviation (between brackets). Altogether, accurate prior results in an average increase in performance of around 23%, while choosing imprecise prior results in less than a 1% of difference.

First of all, when dealing with accurate priors, the gap metric for DC π BO is constantly higher than the one of DCBO, as illustrated by the last line of Table 1a. Such results are statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) according to the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, thus supporting hypothesis **H1**.

Moreover, when using imprecise priors, DC π BO does not perform statistically significantly worse than DCBO. The performance ratio highlighted by the last line of Table 1b

²<https://github.com/lucalavazza/Bayesian-Optimisation-with-Prior-Knowledge>

³<https://github.com/lucalavazza/Simulator-Experiment>

	STAT	IND	MULTIV	NONSTAT	ODE	PISCHAT	ECON
BO	0.47 (0.03)	0.21 (0.03)	0.36 (0.03)	0.53 (0.05)	0.45 (0.03)	0.56 (0.12)	0.35 (0.02)
π BO	0.53 (0.05)	0.40 (0.06)	0.42 (0.04)	0.64 (0.07)	0.51 (0.05)	0.69 (0.17)	0.38 (0.02)
$\Delta \frac{\pi\text{BO}}{\text{BO}}\%$	12.77%	90.48%	16.67%	20.75%	13.33%	22.21%	8.57%
DCBO	0.51 (0.06)	0.17 (0.04)	0.36 (0.04)	0.68 (0.07)	0.60 (0.03)	0.42 (0.08)	0.41 (0.03)
DCπBO	0.58 (0.03)	0.25 (0.05)	0.40 (0.05)	0.77 (0.04)	0.64 (0.01)	0.50 (0.11)	0.51 (0.08)
$\Delta \frac{\text{DC}\pi\text{BO}}{\text{DCBO}}\%$	13.73%	47.06%	11.11%	13.24%	6.67%	19.05%	24.39%

(a) Results when an accurate prior is used.

	STAT	IND	MULTIV	NONSTAT	ODE	PISCHAT	ECON
BO	0.50 (0.01)	0.33 (0.08)	0.41 (0.04)	0.56 (0.02)	0.45 (0.03)	0.55 (0.14)	0.35 (0.02)
π BO	0.49 (0.01)	0.34 (0.09)	0.40 (0.04)	0.55 (0.02)	0.44 (0.03)	0.55 (0.15)	0.35 (0.02)
$\Delta \frac{\pi\text{BO}}{\text{BO}}\%$	-2%	3.03%	-2.44%	-1.79%	-2.22%	0%	0%
DCBO	0.57 (0.01)	0.17 (0.02)	0.36 (0.02)	0.71 (0.05)	0.63 (0.02)	0.46 (0.15)	0.42 (0.03)
DCπBO	0.56 (0.01)	0.17 (0.03)	0.35 (0.02)	0.71 (0.05)	0.62 (0.02)	0.46 (0.15)	0.41 (0.03)
$\Delta \frac{\text{DC}\pi\text{BO}}{\text{DCBO}}\%$	-1.75%	0%	-2.78%	0%	-1.59%	0%	-2.39%

(b) Results when an imprecise prior is used.

Table 1: Results on all the optimisation problems listed in Section 4.1. In brackets is the standard deviation of each experiment. Higher values denote better performances for the gap metric: best in bold also considering hidden decimals.

illustrates that on the averaged gap metric. Moreover, such differences are not statistically significant ($p > 0.01$) according to the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, hence supporting hypothesis **H2**. Also, the use of an imprecise prior does not cause any drawbacks whatsoever compared to DCBO. Computation time and resources used are extremely similar, to the point of being negligible and statistically non-significant, hence we refrained from presenting them.

For completeness, we also test the difference between π BO and BO: in the case of accurate priors, π BO performs better than BO, and the results are statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) while the differences in case of imprecise priors are not statistically significant ($p > 0.01$). Only in the case of NONSTAT, the difference between π BO and BO would have been considered statistically significant for a p-value limit of 0.05. By inspecting Table 1, it is worth noting that when explicit causal and dynamic information are lacking—*i.e.*, for STAT, IND, MULTIV, and PISCHAT—simple BO (or π BO) can have an advantage over DCBO and DC π BO.

	$\beta = 0$	$\beta = 1$	$\beta = 5$	$\beta = 10$
DCBO	0.28 (0.04)	0.30 (0.04)	0.27 (0.02)	0.27 (0.02)
<u>DCπBO</u>	0.28 (0.05)	0.41 (0.05)	0.41 (0.05)	0.40 (0.04)
$\Delta\%$	0%	36.67%	51.85%	48.15%

(a) Results when an accurate prior is used.

	$\beta = 0$	$\beta = 1$	$\beta = 5$	$\beta = 10$
DCBO	0.26 (0.02)	0.26 (0.02)	0.25 (0.01)	0.26 (0.01)
<u>DCπBO</u>	0.27 (0.02)	0.27 (0.02)	0.26 (0.01)	0.26 (0.01)
$\Delta\%$	3.84%	3.84%	4%	0%

(b) Results when an imprecise prior is used.

Table 2: Results of the realistic ECON experiment when performed with different values of the hyperparameter β . In brackets is the standard deviation of each experiment. For the gap metric, higher values denote better performances.

5.3 Post-Hoc Analysis on Hyperparameters

Focusing on the ECON optimisation problem—currently the most realistic case—we report on further post-hoc analyses to determine the role of the hyperparameter β and the impact of the optimisation budget and the number of timesteps T in the Algorithm 1.

The β hyperparameter in the Algorithm 1 represents the degree of confidence in the given prior. For accurate priors (Table 2a), when β is set to be 0, meaning no confidence in the specified prior, it results in DC π BO effectively reverting to DCBO. For $\beta \geq 1$, DC π BO outperforms DCBO, but further modifying β does not seem to result in changes in the performance.

Instead, when an imprecise prior is given, Table 2b shows that the results of the two methods are again very similar since the *Decay Policy* is effective. Therefore, even an algorithmic configuration giving high confidence to the prior will have a limited effect on the results.

The range of most interest is $\beta \in [0, 1]$ when $H = 10$, as per tests, while wider ranges become more interesting as the budget increases. In general, $\beta = 0$ implies no confidence in the prior, effectively immediately reverting the execution of DC π BO to that of DCBO. Increasing the value of β increases the effect of the prior, effectively delaying its loss of influence and increasing the confidence in the prior. This can be observed in Table 2a, where the difference between $\beta = 0$ and $\beta = 1$ is highly noticeable. As the number of iterations increases, all executions get increasingly similar to DCBO, explaining why different Beta values produce highly similar results when an imprecise prior is used. Concluding, the best value of the hyperparameter Beta is highly empirical and tied to the value of H.

Figure 4: Convergence of the ECON experiment with the use of an accurate prior (a) and of an imprecise prior (b).

Varying the budget and the number of available timesteps T assigned for each execution, we can appreciate the impact on the identified optimal solution. Figure 4 depicts the convergence of the methods using an accurate and an imprecise prior, where the dotted lines represent the ground truth for each time step. The value on the x -axis is the cost of each execution, *i.e.*, the number of iterations given as a budget to Algorithm 1. The lighter shades of colours in the graphs represent the spectra of the results from all the executions of the methods, while the stronger coloured lines represent the average result from all the executions for each method. The difference of the optimal value between $t = 0$ and $t = 1$ is due to the different relationships between variables in the DAG associated with the SCM, *cf.*, Figure 3.

Figure 4 illustrates well the effect of considering the dynamic and causal information compared to pure BO: DCBO and DC π BO perform better and converge faster. Due to the wide y -axis range, the differences between DCBO and DC π BO are less noticeable while still present, *cf.*, Table 1. When an accurate prior is used, we can observe that the spectrum of π BO is narrower and more focused than that of BO, denoting more accurate and consistent results, while also converging faster. On the other hand, when an imprecise prior is used, π BO's spectrum starts larger, denoting worse initial performances as expected, which eventually do not hinder the final results.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we present a powerful approach for optimising a black-box function that takes into account causal and temporal dependencies, while also leveraging prior knowledge from domain experts. Our method, termed Dynamic Causal Bayesian Optimisation with Prior Knowledge (DC π BO), empowers users to provide a function that reflects their intuition about the location of the optima. By incorporating this function into the search process, our approach yields superior results.

Our extensive experimental analysis over both synthetic and realistic optimisation problems (Sections 4.1 and 5) shows that the use of DC π BO, alongside an accurate prior, produces better results than the state-of-the-art approach DCBO, *cf.*, Table 1. At the same time, DC π BO produces comparable results where an imprecise prior is chosen. Our post-hoc analysis of a real-world optimisation problem concerning a closed economy (Sections 1 and 4.1), which employs real data from the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and a realistic large-scale structure for its DAG associated with the SCM, also shows the effect of using different values for the algorithm’s hyperparameters. This sheds further light on why an imprecise prior does not, in any case, hinder the execution.

In future work, we will look at learning the SCM and the associated DAG, also considering the case where a domain expert provides prior knowledge of the relationships among variables. We also aim at building on top of recent advancements in reinforcement learning (Seitzer et al., 2021) to deploy DC π BO when exploring a partially observable environment with high-level causal knowledge and prior information on the optimal policy.

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